

International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management (IJMFM)

ISSN: 2348 -3954 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 -2546 (Print)

Email us: editor@arseam.com

<http://www.arseam.com/>

Download Full Paper:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-2-issue-9-oct-2014>

**Impact
Factor:
0.98**

FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF INDIAN INSURANCE COMPANIES USING RATIO ANALYSIS

Ms. Gurjeet Kaur

Assistant Professor (Finance),

Kamal Institute of Higher Education and Advance Technology, GGSIPU, Delhi, India

Abstract

The objective of this paper is to compare the financial performance of public and private life and non-life insurance companies with the help of solvency ratio. The major life insurance companies are Life Insurance Corporation of India, Bajaj Allianz Life Insurance Company, HDFC Standard Life Insurance Company, ICICI Prudential Life Insurance Company and Birla Sunlife Insurance Company Limited. The major non-life insurance companies are National Insurance Company Limited, ICICI Lombard General Insurance Company Limited, Royal Sundaram Alliance Insurance Company Limited, Reliance General Insurance Company Limited and Tata AIG Insurance Company Limited. In practice, the insurance sector is a colossal one and is growing at a speedy rate of 15-20% together with banking services, insurance services contribute as about 7% to the country's GDP. Although, in Life Insurance Companies, Bajaj Allianz secured first position by maintaining a high solvency ratio over 7 years and LIC stood last. ICICI Lombard secured first position in solvency ratio among all the non-life insurance companies followed by Tata AIG and Reliance. National General stood fourth and Royal Sundaram stood last. The study also revealed that in case of life insurers the difference in the solvency ratio between public and private sector was significant while in case of non-life insurers the difference was insignificant.

Key Words: Companies, Life Insurance, Non-Life Insurance, Performance, Solvency, Public Sector, Private Sector.

Introduction

With 36 crore policies, India's life insurance sector is the biggest in the world. The sector consists of 52 insurance companies, of which 24 are in life insurance business and 28 in non-life. Among the life insurers, Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) is the sole public sector company. Apart from that, among the non-life insurers there are six public sector insurers. In addition to these, there is sole national re-insurer, namely, General Insurance Corporation of India. Other stakeholders in Indian Insurance market include Agents (Individual and Corporate), Brokers, Surveyors and Third Party Administrators servicing Health Insurance claims.

Out of 28 non-life insurance companies, 5 private sector insurers are registered to underwrite policies exclusively in Health, Personal Accident and Travel insurance segments. They are Star Health and Allied Insurance Company Ltd, Apollo Munich Health Insurance Company Ltd, Max Bupa Health Insurance Company Ltd, Religare Health Insurance

Company Ltd and Cigna TTK Health Insurance Company Ltd. There are two more specialised insurers belonging to public sector, namely, Export Credit Guarantee Corporation of India for Credit Insurance and Agriculture Insurance Company Ltd for Crop Insurance.

The life insurance industry in the country is projected to increase at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 12-15 per cent in the next five years. The industry plans to hike penetration levels to five per cent by 2020, and has the potential to top the US\$ 1 trillion mark over the next seven years.

The optimistic outlook is helped to a large degree by the Government of India's efforts to strengthen the sector. The Union Cabinet in July 2014 approved a proposal to relax foreign direct investment (FDI) limit in the domestic insurance sector to 49 per cent from 26 per cent, signalling the government's intent to draw capital and investment into the sector.

Insurance penetration of India i.e. premium collected by Indian insurers is 3.96 % of GDP in FY 2012-13. Per capita premium underwritten i.e. insurance density in India during FY 2012-13 is US\$ 53.2. However there has been gradual decrease in the market share witnessed by all the public insurers. In this context, this paper attempts to analyse the performance of Indian insurance companies through solvency ratio.

The Literature Review

In order to evaluate the financial performance of insurance sector, the researchers, academicians and policy makers have investigated several studies in different perspectives and in different time periods. Sharma Vikas, Chowhan S.S. (2013) analyzed and compared the performance of public and private life insurance companies in India. Neelaveni V. (2012) evaluated the financial performance and studied the products of the life insurance companies. Tiwari Anushuja, Yadav Babita (2012) analyzed the condition of life insurance industry in post liberalization and the overall impact of liberalization on life insurance business in terms of total premium income, total income, market share and number of policies. Srivastava Arnika, Tripathi Sarika (2012) analyzed the changing trends of Indian life insurance companies for the period of six years from 2001-02 to 2007-08. It was found that insurance industry contributes to the financial sector of an economy and also provides an important social security net in developing countries. Gour Bhuvnesh, Gupta M.C (2012) analyzed the solvency ratio of five life insurance companies of India for the period of three years from 2009-2010 to 2011-12. They also investigated whether the performance of different companies is similar to each other or is there any significant difference in that. Singh Manjit, Kumar Rohit (2009) evaluated the emerging trends in the growth and performance of General Insurance Companies in India and appraised the competitive financial performance of the Public Sector and the Private Sector General Insurance Companies in India and suggested the strategies for improving the performance of General Insurance Companies in India.

Solvency of Life Insurance and Non-Life Insurance Companies

Solvency is the ability of a company to meet its long-term financial obligations. The solvency of an insurance company corresponds to its ability to pay claims. The solvency ratio is a way investors can measure the company's ability to meet its long term obligations. An insurer is insolvent if its assets are not adequate (over indebtedness) or cannot be disposed of in time to pay the claims arising. In other words, it is the extra capital that an insurance company is required to hold.

As per the IRDA (Assets, Liabilities, and Solvency Margin of Insurers) Rules 2000, both life and general insurance companies need to maintain solvency margins. Life insurance companies are expected to maintain a 150% solvency margin. The higher the ratio is the better equipped a company is to pay off its debts and survive in the long term.

All insurance companies have to pay claims to policy holders. These could be current or future claims of policy holders. Insurers are expected to put aside a certain sum to cover these liabilities. These are also referred to as technical provisions. Insurance, however, is risky business and unforeseen events might occur sometimes, resulting in higher claims not anticipated earlier.

The solvency margin is designed to take care of problems that are usually not anticipated. It also provides elbow room to the managers of insurers to rectify problems and take precautionary measures.

Table 1 represents the mean and comparative analysis of the five life insurance companies for a period of seven years, i.e., from 2005-06 to 2011-12 and the result showed Bajaj Allianz Life Insurance Company secured first position in mean analysis of solvency ratio among all the life insurance companies followed by ICICI Prudential Life Insurance Company and Birla Sunlife Insurance Company Limited. HDFC Standard Life stood fourth and LIC stood last in the mean analysis of solvency ratio. The company should have a management who stay ready for payment of claims and surrenders, so that it can increase its solvency ratio in the succeeding years. Risks due to investments not being able to be liquidated at the right time and in a proper manner should not be there in the company.

Table 2 represents the mean and comparative analysis of five non-life insurance companies for a seven year period and it was found that ICICI Lombard General Insurance Company Limited has the highest mean, i.e., 1.92. ICICI Lombard secured first position in solvency ratio among all the non-life insurance companies followed by Tata AIG and Reliance. Royal Sundaram stood fourth and National General stood last in the mean analysis of solvency ratio. The company should match its assets to the liabilities so that it can increase the solvency. Risk of the loss of receivables due from insurance intermediaries and risk that external third parties do not meet their obligations should not be presented in the companies.

One way ANOVA test is applied for determining whether there is any significant difference in solvency ratios between the LIC and different private life insurance companies. (The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level). Table 3 represents the One way ANOVA analysis of LIC and other private life insurance Companies. In the table, the p value is .002. The significance value is less than .05. Hence, it can be said that there is a significant difference in the solvency ratios of LIC and other private insurance company.

Table 4 represents the One way ANOVA analysis of National General Insurance Company Ltd and other private non-life insurance Companies. In the table, the p value is .188. The significance value is more than .05. Hence, it can be said that there is no significant difference in the solvency ratios of National General Insurance Co Ltd and other private non-life insurance company.

The study also applied one way ANOVA analysis to examine if the difference in the solvency ratio between public and private sector is significant. The analysis revealed that in case of life insurers the difference was significant while in case of non-life insurers the difference was insignificant. This was due to the fact that in life insurance companies, LIC maintained only the stipulated 1.5 solvency ratio, whereas other private sector insurance companies had solvency ratio as high as 5.15 (Bajaj Allianz). However, in case of non-life insurance companies, all the companies were close to 1.5 solvency ratio only and hence significant difference was not observed.

Table-1: A Comparative Analysis of five Life Insurance Company based on Solvency Ratio of seven years

Companies	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	Mean
LIC	1.30	1.50	1.52	1.54	1.54	1.54	1.54	1.50
Bajaj Allianz	2.80	2.45	2.34	2.62	2.68	2.86	5.15	2.99
HDFC Standard Life	2.90	2.05	2.38	2.58	1.80	1.72	1.88	2.19
ICICI Prudential	2.60	1.53	1.74	2.31	2.90	3.27	3.71	2.58
Birla Sun Life	2.00	1.80	2.37	2.44	2.11	2.89	2.99	2.37

Source: Compiled from the Annual Reports of Insurance Companies

Note: Solvency = Available solvency margin / Required solvency margin

Table-2: A Comparative Analysis of five Non-Life Insurance Company based on Solvency Ratio of seven years

Companies	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	Mean
National General	1.08	1.70	2.22	1.56	1.00	1.34	1.60	1.50
ICICI Lombard	2.19	2.18	2.03	2.03	2.07	1.56	1.36	1.92
Royal Sundaram Allianz	1.66	1.64	1.59	1.64	1.39	1.56	1.36	1.55
Reliance General	3.04	1.95	1.64	1.59	1.70	1.15	1.66	1.82
Tata AIG	1.68	1.85	1.91	1.98	1.88	1.68	2.16	1.88

Source: Compiled from the Annual Reports of Insurance Companies

Note: Solvency = Available solvency margin / Required solvency margin

Table-3: One way ANOVA Analysis of LIC and other private life insurance Companies					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	8.457	4	2.114	5.366	.002
Within Groups	11.819	30	.394		
Total	20.276	34			

The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table-4: One way ANOVA Analysis of National General Insurance Co Ltd and other private non-life insurance companies

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.815	4	.204	1.649	.188
Within Groups	3.704	30	.123		
Total	4.519	34			

The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Conclusion

Solvency of a life insurer is heavily dependent on the returns received from total investible funds and the interest rate. It has to be maintained by all the insurance companies in India whether it's Private or Public sector. All the companies are at same level, some of them are old, some are new, some are big and some are small, but it's same for all and everything is under IRDA norms and scrutiny. So, which company is safe or unsafe is not relevant now. Risk is with every company and that is equal for all.

References

Sharma Vikas, Chowhan S.S. (2013), "A Comparative Study of Public & Private Life Insurance", *Indian Journal of Applied Studies*, Vol.3, No.1, pp.93-94.

Neelaveni V. (2012), "Financial Performance of Life Insurance Companies and Products", *ZENITH International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research*, Vol.2, No.3, pp.233-258.

Tiwari Anushuja, Yadav Babita (2012), "Analytical Study on Indian Life Insurance Industry in Post Liberalization", *International Journal of Social Science Tomorrow* Vol. 1 No. 2, pp.1-10.

Srivastava Arnika, Tripathi Sarika (2011), "Indian Life Insurance Industry- The Changing Trends", *Journal of Arts, Science & Commerce*, Vol.3, No.2, pp.93-98.

Gour Bhuvnesh, Gupta M.C (2012), "A Review on Solvency Margin in Indian Insurance Companies", *International Journal of Recent Research and Review*, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp.43-47.

Singh Manjit, Kumar Rohit (2009), "Emerging Trends in Financial Performance of General Insurance Industry in India", *Indian Management Studies Journal*, pp. 31-44.

http://www.irda.gov.in/ADMINCMS/cms/NormalData_Layout.aspx?page=PageNo4&mid=2
Accessed on 5th September 2014.

http://www.irda.gov.in/ADMINCMS/cms/frmGeneral_Layout.aspx?page=PageNo1848&flag=1&mid=Annual%20reports%20%3E%3E%20Annual%20reports%20of%20the%20Authority
Accessed on 15th September 2014.

<http://www.ibef.org/industry/insurance-sector-india.aspx> Accessed on 7th October 2014.

http://www.policyholder.gov.in/indian_insurance_market.aspx Accessed on 8th October 2014.